

1 SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

1.1 Experimental protocol

The complete experimental session spanned 3 days. The detailed protocol performed by Subject 1-AMI is provided below. The first 2 days involved a training session based on visual feedback of EMG activation, during which the prosthesis was powered OFF. On the third day, the participant controlled the ankle prosthesis using our proposed EMG control framework during different movements

1.1.1 Day 1 - Prosthesis alignment and Channel selection

- Alignment of the prosthesis

A certified prosthetist from the Roessingh Rehabilitation Center performed a static and dynamic prosthesis alignment.

- EMG activation channel selection

- Placement of 8 bipolar electrodes (4 in case of Subject 3) to cover the entire belly of 2 muscles of the stump, namely the *gastrocnemius medialis* (GM) and *tibialis anterior*(TA).
- The participant was instructed to activate the TA and GM of the stump alternately while sitting and not wearing his socket.
- The participant was instructed to activate the TA and GM of the stump alternately while sitting and wearing his socket.
- Walking trial with visual feedback to choose the channel for each muscle.

The trial was meant to select one EMG signal channel from each muscle of interest among $c = \{GM, TA\}$ that most approximate the activation patterns of intact limb individuals. The use of visual feedback of one selected EMG signal channel at a time allows us to verify the controllability over the muscle contraction given a reference curve to follow. Moreover, this allowed us to collect preliminary data useful for the calibration of the model, and it functioned as a first training session.

1.1.2 Day 2 - Adaptation with an unpowered active prosthesis

The session had the purpose of evaluating if the participant could re-learn muscle excitation patterns following a predefined pattern.

- EMG activation channel selection
 - Placement of EMG electrodes
 - Walking trial at preferred speed

The trial was meant to select one EMG activation channel from each muscle of interest among $c = \{GM, TA\}$ that most approximate the activation patterns of intact limb individuals.

- Maximum voluntary contraction (MVC) measurement

Maximum effort isometric plantarflexion and dorsiflexion while sitting and standing for 10 times in each direction. Maximum values were used for the normalization of EMG activation signals.

- Walking at self-selected speed with visual feedback of GM

The participant walked on the treadmill at his preferred speed. The goal of the trial was to adapt to our interface and learn how to modulate his muscle contraction following the reference. This trial was repeated twice with a duration of 10 minutes each. The trial was interrupted earlier if the participant expressed fatigue.

- Walking at self-selected speed with visual feedback from TA

Same as for the GM

1.1.3 Day 3 - Adaptation and Walking trial

- Instrumentation

Placement of EMG electrodes and 37 motion capture markers

- Bilateral calf raise under metronome with the prosthesis ON

For this test, the participant performed one full cycle of the calf raise movement per beat, therefore at the beep, the participant would apply torque at the ankle and raise from the ground, hold the plantar-flexed position for a fraction of a second, and then return to the natural position with the heel on the ground. The metronome was set for cadences of 30, 45, and 60 beats per minute (bpm). The participant was not able to follow the 60bpm cadence, therefore results are not included.

- Treadmill walking at 3 different speeds with the prosthesis ON

The participant walked at his preferred speed ($v_0 = 2km/h$) for 45 seconds, at speed $v_1 = 1.2 \times v_0 = 2.4km/h$ for 45 seconds and at speed $v_1 = 0.8 \times v_0 = 1.6km/h$ for 45 seconds.

- Treadmill walking at 2 different speeds with the prosthesis ON

The participant walked at his preferred speed ($v_0 = 2km/h$) for 45 seconds and at speed $v_1 = 1.2v_0 = 2.4km/h$ for 45 seconds.

2 FIGURES AND TABLES

Table S1. Time between peaks of muscle activations, prosthetic joint angles, and active prosthesis torques in the plantar flexion direction, for the metronome cadence of 30 and 45 bpm in the calf raise exercise.

Signal	30 bpm	45 bpm
Myoneural Activation	2.0±0.1	1.4±0.1
Torques	2.0±0.5	1.4±0.1
Angle	2.7±3.5	1.6±1.2

Table S2. Amplitudes of EMGs and active prosthesis joint torques in the plantarflexion and dorsiflexion directions, for the walking inclinations of ground, 3% and, 5% in Subject 2-AMI

	ground	3%	5%
GM	0.32±0.17	0.38±0.12	0.38±0.12
TA	0.32±0.17	0.38±0.12	0.63±0.19
active prosthesis torque	-29.5±17.4	-37.7±16	-40.7±17.1

Table S3. Amplitudes of EMGs and active prosthesis joint torques in the plantarflexion and dorsiflexion directions, for the walking inclinations of ground, 3% and, 5% in Subject 3-OI

	ground	3%	5%
GM	0.53±0.29	0.23±0.23	0.18±0.28
TA	0.18±0.12	0.25±0.22	0.09±0.13
active prosthesis torque	-35.2±23.7	-14.2±8.2	-29.1±26.3

Table S4. Correlation coefficient between participants' activation patterns and healthy activation patterns

R	GM-Day 1	GM-Day 3	TA-Day 1	TA-Day 3
Subject 1-AMI	0.53	0.94	0.66	0.03
Subject 2-AMI	0.32	0.86	0.01	-0.18
Subject 3-OI	0.36	0.07	-0.04	0.47

Figure S1. Schematics of the EMG-driven-Neuromechanical Model-Based controller, calibrated from participant-specific data of the intact leg (B-E). Experimental EMG activations and joint angle data (A) are inputs to the model. EMG activations are filtered (B) to obtain activation envelopes (details in the methods section), accounting for a participant-specific excitation-to-activation shape factor. The Musculotendon Kinematic Stage (C) synthesizes subject-specific paths of musculotendon units (MTUs) by utilizing a set of MTU-specific cubic B-splines. Each B-spline calculates the MTU length and moment arms based on the input joint angles. The Musculotendon Dynamics Stage (D) determines the dynamic equilibrium between muscle fibers and series-elastic tendons to produce the net MTU force. It utilizes a Hill-type muscle model informed by MTU length and muscle activations from the preceding 2 stages. The Moment Computation Stage (E) transfers MTU forces to the skeletal joint level using MTU moment arms. The motorized prosthesis operates in closed-loop current control (F). Torque commands are converted into current commands via the motor constant (k_t) and transmission ratio (r).

Figure S2. Time in seconds between peaks of muscle activations for GM (blue) and TA (red) and active prosthesis torques, during the walking trial on a treadmill on the second day of experimental sessions.

Figure S3. Averaged Joint torques at different ground elevations. Solid lines indicate averages and, shaded areas standard deviations result of the active prosthesis torques. Dashed lines are EMG-driven NMBC-decoded torques (more details in section Materials and Methods). Each participant performed treadmill walking at three different elevation: ground (red), 3% elevation (blue), and 5% elevation (green).

Figure S4. Averaged muscle activations at different ground elevations. Solid lines indicate averages and, shaded areas standard deviations result. Each participant performed treadmill walking at three different elevation: ground (red), 3% elevation (blue), and 5% elevation (green).

Subject 1-AMI

Figure S5. Histograms of peak muscle activations (row 1), torques (row 2), and peak angular velocities (row 3) of the prosthetic ankle joint of plantarflexors (or plantarflexion) during metronome dictated calf raise task for cadences of 30 and 45 beats per minute (bps) on the third day of experiments (a) of Subject 1-AMI. Muscle activations of GM (b) and TA (c), as well as active prosthesis ankle torques (d) and angles (e), are also depicted. Dashed lines are NMBC torques unconstrained by the limits of the prosthesis. The participant performed a plantarflexion at each beep and returned to the natural position with heels on the ground.